

ELIXIR Compute Platform Face-to-Face Event Summary Report 2024

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Background

ELIXIR, the European Research Infrastructure for life science data has five different Platforms focused on life science technical activities - these are Tools, Training, Compute, Data, and Interoperability. The [ELIXIR Compute Platform](#) held their annual Face-to-Face meeting on the 24-25th January, 2024 in Brno, Czech Republic. The Face-to-Face meeting was kindly hosted by local Compute Platform Executive Committee (ExCo) members Jana Broncova and Ludek Matyska, supported through [ELIXIR-CZ](#) and Masaryk University. This year's meeting brought together members of the Compute Platform in order to kick off the new work programme for the 2024-2026 period.

Event format and content

The event took place at the Courtyard Hotel Marriott in Brno, CZ for in-person attendees and a remote stream facilitated online attendance for those unable to join in-person. A total of 52 participants joined the event over the two days. Of these attendees, 32 were in-person and 20 attendees streamed the event online.

Day 1 of the event was kicked off by a presentation by local ExCo, Jana Broncova and welcome by ELIXIR's Programme Manager for Scientific Computing, Jonathan Tedds. An overview of the new Compute Platform 2024-2026 programme and its overall goals was then presented by ExCo Juha Törnroos of CSC, Finland. This led into flash talk introductions and in depth discussions on the four key ELIXIR Compute Platform work packages:

- WP2: Advanced Service Access Control
- WP3: Protected access to sensitive data for analysis
- WP4: Multi Cloud Infrastructure Deployment
- WP5: Sustainability, Accounting and Provenance for Federated Analytics

Corinne Martin of the ELIXIR Hub provided an interactive session on the importance of measuring and presenting impact in relation to Compute Platform services. This was followed by overviews on large EC initiatives; [EuroHPC](#) by Juha Törnroos (FI) and [EOSC](#) by Ludek Matyska (CZ). Advice and expertise was provided and discussed on aligning the ELIXIR Compute Platform activities with these major European initiatives.

The day closed with expert overviews on newly funded EC projects coordinated or involving ELIXIR and having particular relevance to the ELIXIR Compute Platform:

- [EOSC OSCARS](#) by Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub)
- [EOSC EVERSE](#) by project PI, Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR)
- [EOSC ENTRUST](#) by Stefan Negru (ELIXIR-FI)
- [ELIXIR STEERS](#) by project PI, Andy Smith (ELIXIR Hub)

Day 2 of the event focused on discussion on alignments between the ELIXIR Hub coordinated [Genomic Data Infrastructure \(GDI\)](#) project and the Compute Platform, presented by Jonathan Tedds (Hub). Following this discussion Martin Kuba (ELIXIR-CZ) presented on the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA₄GH) Passports standard for researcher identity and access management in the [GA₄GH DURi workstream](#). These are two key international efforts working to enable federated analytics for sensitive datasets and align closely to the Compute Platform's ambitions in the [ELIXIR 2024-2028 Programme](#).

The Compute Platform work package leads led breakout sessions with their members and reported back on their kick-off progress. Advancements were made and key discussion areas tackled included practical aspects such as setting work packages calls in place, and more focused strategic discussions such as targeting the work package initial milestones and deliverables due during 2024.

Significant event outcomes

- Participants old and new were briefed and aligned on the new Compute Platform 2024-2026 work programme areas.
- Alignments and clarity on large EC initiatives were identified relating to:
 - EOSC
 - EuroHPC
- Alignment and clarity on new and ongoing EC funded projects were identified including:
 - EOSC OSCARS
 - EOSC EVERSE
 - EOSC ENTRUST
 - ELIXIR STEERS
 - GDI
- Scope of work packages under new work programme were clarified such as:
 - WP5: aligning to potential project funding sources to bolster this new area of work.
- Members' understanding was broadened relating to funding opportunities, particularly those from the EC Horizon programme and the importance of forward planning.
- The ELIXIR Compute Platform 2024-2026 work packages were officially kicked off.

Participant feedback on the event

Post-event survey responses were received from approximately a quarter of the event attendees, providing insights on various aspects of the event. The streaming experience received positive feedback. However, some respondents noted occasional audio limitations during hybrid presentations due to an in room echo. Participants also suggested that future event editions could consider slightly longer break times, as this would be welcomed by attendees.

Conclusion

The Compute Platform held another successful hybrid F2F event during 2024. Significant progress was made to kick off the new 2024-2026 current Platform work programme and related work packages. Planning was successfully undertaken by work package leads and members for the activities of the coming year. Looking beyond the Compute Platform and towards complementary

larger EC projects and initiatives, a great deal of synergistic initiatives were identified and discussed for planning alignments to the work of the ELIXIR Compute Platform members.

Members of the ELIXIR Compute Platform in Brno Czech Republic, 24th January 2024.